

Facile synthesis of some oxazepine-steroid using three component system

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Abstract

There is a great interest in the development of several oxazepine derivatives in both pharmacy and organic chemistry fields such as antidepressant (amoxapine) and schizophrenia (loxapine). In search of new oxazepine analogs some methods use several reagents; however, some of these reagents are expensive and require special conditions for their handling. Therefore, the aim of this study was synthesizing some oxazepine-steroid using three component system (steroid, acetonitrile derivatives and 5-hexyn-1-ol). The chemical structure a purity of compounds was confirmed by melting point, infrared spectra, NMR spectroscopic data and mass spectrometry. The results shown the following; 1) the reagents used for the preparation of oxazepine derivatives does not require special conditions and are facile of handling; 2) the yielding of oxazepine derivatives are relatively good. All these data indicate that production of oxazepine derivatives could be carried out on a larger scale.

Keywords: Estradiol, Estrone, 4-nitroestradiol and 4-nitroestrone, Oxazepine, Spectroscopic.

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1. Introduction

For several years there has been a great interest in the development of oxazepines in both pharmacy [1, 2] and organic chemistry field [3,4]. There are several studies which shown the preparation of some oxazepine derivatives; for example, the synthesis of 5,6-benz-1,3-oxazepine-4,7-dione derivatives from a semicarbazone [5]. Other data indicate the synthesis of benzo-1,4-oxazepine derivatives via tandem transformation of C-N coupling/C-H carbonylation [6]. In addition, a report showed the preparation of a 1,3-oxazepine derivative through cycloaddition of vinyloxiranes to sulfamate-derived cyclic [7]. Also, other study indicates the synthesis of some oxazepine derivatives via intramolecular amination of cyclopropylmethyl cation [8]. Additionally, other

data showed the reaction of N-Sulfonyl-1,2,3-triazoles with glycidol to form 1,4-oxazepines [9]. Also, 1,4-oxazepines were synthesized from an alkynyl-alcohol [10]. Recently, an oxazepine was prepared by Copper-catalyzed intramolecular reaction between O-propargyl oxime a dipolarophile derivative. [11]

All these data shown the preparation several oxazepine derivatives using several protocols which involves several reagents; however, some of these reagents are difficult to handle require and special conditions. Therefore, in this study were synthesized some oxazepine-steroid derivatives from estradiol, estrone, 4-nitroestradiol and 4-nitroestrone (Figure 1) using some tool chemicals.

Figure 1. Chemical structure of estradiol, estrone, 4-nitroestradiol and 4-nitroestrone. [12]

2. Experimental

2.1. Chemical synthesis

Both 4-nitroestradiol and 4-nitroestrone were prepared using previously methods reported [12]. In addition, all the reagents handled in this research were obtained from Sigma-Aldrich Sigma-Aldrich Co., Ltd. Melting point of compounds was evaluated using an Electrothermal (900 model). Infrared spectrum (IR) was determined using potassium bromide with a Perkin Elmer Lambda 40 apparatus. ^1H and ^{13}C NMR spectrum was analyzed on a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz (megahertz) in CDCl_3 (deuterated chloroform) using TMS as an internal standard. EIMS spectrum was obtained with a Finnigan Trace Gas Chromatography Polaris Q-Spectrometer. Elementary analysis was determined using a Perkin Elmer Ser. II CHNS/02400 apparatus.

2.2. Preparation of nitrophenyl-oxazapentacyclo-steroid derivative (5-8)

In a round bottom flask (10 ml), **1** or **2** or **3** or **4** (0.50 mmol), (4-Nitro-phenyl)-acetonitrile (90 mg; 0.55 mmol), 5-hexyn-1-ol (90 μl , 0.82 mmol) and 5 ml of ethanol (3:5) were stirring to reflux for 8 h. The solvent of the mixture obtained was removed under reduced pressure and purified through a crystallization using the methanol:hexane:water (4:2:1) system.

5-methyl-17-[(4-nitrophenyl)methyl]-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0^{5,9}.0^{15,21}]docosa-1(22), 13,17,19-tetraen-6-ol (**5**)

yielding 56% of **5**; m.p. 118-120°C; IR (ν_{max} , cm^{-1}) 3400, 3320, 1382 and 1130; ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_{H} : 0.80 (s, 3H), 1.12-1.96 (m, 12H), 2.04-3.70 (m, 6H), 4.00 (m, 2H), 5.10-5.60 (m, 2H), 5.86 (d, 1H, $J = 1.82$ Hz), 6.40 (broad,

1H), 7.20 (d, 1H, J = 1.60 Hz), 7.50-8.20 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 11.32, 23.04, 25.82, 30.74, 31.35, 36.86, 36.88, 38.92, 39.00, 40.72, 43.63, 50.10, 50.47, 78.92, 81.74, 113.86, 21.34, 124.23, 130.24, 130.53, 130.54, 130.75, 141.54, 149.00, 149.44, 158.86 ppm. EI-MS m/z: 460.23 Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₃₂N₂O₄: C, 73.02; H, 7.00; N, 6.08; O, 13.90. Found: C, 73.00; H, 7.00.

5-methyl-17-[(4-nitrophenyl)methyl]-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetraen-6-one (6)

yielding 45% of **6**; m.p. 136-140°C; IR (V_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3322, 1722, 1380 and 1132: ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_H: 0.90 (s, 3H), 1.20-1.96 (m, 9H), 2.10-3.70 (m, 8H), 4.00 (m, 2H), 5.10-5.60 (m, 2H), 5.86 (d, 1H, J = 1.82 Hz), 7.20 (d, 1H, J = 1.60 Hz), 7.50-8.20 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 13.84, 21.50, 25.80, 26.35, 31.34, 35.74, 36.86, 39.02, 39.03, 40.72, 47.38, 52.290, 53.33, 78.92, 113.86, 121.37, 124.20, 126.59, 130.27, 130.53, 133.24, 141.52, 149.44, 150.52, 158.82, 220.15 ppm. EI-MS m/z: 458.22 Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₃₀N₂O₄: C, 73.34; H, 6.59; N, 6.11; O, 13.96. Found: C, 73.30; H, 6.52.

5-methyl-14-nitro-17-[(4-nitrophenyl)methyl]-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetraen-6-ol (7)

yielding 45% of **7**; m.p. 145-147°C; IR (V_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3402, 3320, 1380 and 1130: ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_H: 0.80 (s, 3H), 1.10-1.96 (m, 10H), 2.10-3.64 (m, 7H), 4.02 (m, 2H), 4.60-5.10 (m, 2H), 6.00 (d, 1H, J = 1.82 Hz), 6.40 (broad, 1H), 7.22 (d, 1H, J = 1.60 Hz), 7.50-8.20 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 11.32, 23.02, 27.92, 30.70, 36.82, 38.31, 39.07, 42.56, 43.62, 48.59, 52.02, 76.49, 81.72, 121.92, 124.20, 128.40, 130.16, 130.32, 130.50, 134.52, 143.82, 144.52, 149.44, 174.84 ppm EI-MS m/z: 505.22 Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₃₁N₃O₃: C, 66.52; H, 6.18; N, 8.31; O, 18.99. Found: C, 66.48; H, 6.12.

5-methyl-14-nitro-17-[(4-nitrophenyl)methyl]-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetraen-6-one (8)

yielding 59% of **8**; m.p. 112-114°C; IR (V_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3320, 1720, 1384, and 1132: ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_H: 0.90 (s, 3H), 1.20-1.96 (m, 7H), 2.06-3.64 (m, 9H), 4.00 (m, 2H), 4.60-5.10 (m, 2H), 6.00 (d, 1H, J = 1.82 Hz), 7.22 (d, 1H, J = 1.60

Hz), 7.50-8.20 (m, 4H) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 13.84, 21.50, 25.80, 26.33, 31.36, 35.74, 36.86, 39.00, 39.02, 40.70, 47.38, 52.22, 54.86, 53.33, 78.90, 113.88, 121.40, 124.20, 126.56, 130.26, 130.50, 133.22, 141.53, 149.43, 150.52, 158.82, 220.20 ppm. EI-MS m/z: 458.22 Anal. Calcd. for C₂₈H₂₉N₃O₆: C, 73.34; H, 6.59; N, 6.11; O, 13.96. Found: C, 73.30; H, 6.50.

2.3. Preparation of oxa-azapentacyclo-steroid derivative (9-12)

In a round bottom flask (10 ml), **5** or **6** or **7** or **8** (0.50 mmol), 5-hexyn-1-ol (90 μl, 0.82 mmol) and 5 ml of acetonitrile:ethanol (1:4) were stirring to reflux for 8 h. The solvent of the mixture obtained was removed under reduced pressure and purified through a crystallization using the ethanol:hexane:water (4:2:2) system.

5,17-dimethyl-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0-0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetraen-6-ol (9)

yielding 44% of **9**; m.p. 98-100°C; IR (V_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3400, 3322, and 1130: ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_H: 0.80 (s, 3H), 1.10-1.96 (m, 12H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 2.02-5.60 (m, 8H), 5.86 (d, 1H, J = 1.82 Hz), 6.40 (broad, 1H), 7.20 (d, 1H, J = 1.60 Hz) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 11.32, 15.85, 23.02, 25.82, 30.73, 31.35, 36.88, 38.95, 39.00, 40.70, 43.62, 50.05, 50.44, 77.36, 81.72, 113.80, 121.55, 126.53, 130.24, 130.74, 149.90, 159.52 ppm. EI-MS m/z: 339.21. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₉NO₂: C, 77.84; H, 8.61; N, 4.13; O, 9.43. Found: C, 77.78; H, 8.58.

5,17-dimethyl-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo[11.9.0-0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetraen-6-one (10)

yielding 56% of **10**; m.p. 134-140°C; IR (V_{max}, cm⁻¹) 3322, 1722, and 1130: ¹H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_H: 0.90 (s, 3H), 1.20-1.96 (m, 9H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 2.10-5.60 (m, 10H), 5.86 (d, 1H, J = 1.82 Hz), 7.20 (d, 1H, J = 1.60 Hz) ppm. ¹³C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_C: 13.87, 15.86, 21.53, 25.80, 26.35, 31.38, 35.74, 39.00, 39.02, 40.70, 47.38, 52.22, 53.30, 77.35, 113.80, 121.52, 126.59, 129.24, 130.24, 151.40, 159.53, 220.20 ppm. EI-MS m/z: 337.20. Anal. Calcd. for C₂₂H₂₇NO₂: C, 78.30; H, 8.06; N, 4.15; O, 9.48. Found: C, 78.24; H, 8.00.

5,17-dimethyl-14-nitro-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo [11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0⁵.⁹.0¹⁵.²¹]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetra en-6-ol (11)

yielding 52% of **11**; m.p. 122-124°C; IR (V_{\max} , cm^{-1}) 3400, 3320, 1380 and 1130: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_{H} : 0.80 (s, 3H), 1.10-1.96 (m, 10H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 2.02-5.00 (m, 9H), 6.00 (d, 1H, $J = 1.82$ Hz), 6.40 (broad, 1H), 7.20 (d, 1H, $J = 1.60$ Hz) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_{C} : 11.32, 15.85, 23.02, 27.93, 30.03, 0.36, 30.72, 38.32, 39.07, 42.56, 43.62, 48.59, 52.00, 74.93, 81.72, 122.13, 128.36, 130.12, 130.34, 130.53, 145.41, 175.60 ppm. EI-MS m/z : 384.20. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{28}\text{N}_2\text{O}_2$: C, 68.73; H, 7.34; N, 7.29; O, 16.65. Found: C, 68.70; H, 7.30.

5,17-dimethyl-14-nitro-16-oxa-18-azapentacyclo [11.9.0.0^{2,10}.0^{5,9}.0^{15,21}]docosa-1(22),13,17,19-tetra en-6-one (12)

yielding 65% of **12**; m.p. 136-140°C; IR (V_{\max} , cm^{-1}) 3322, 1722, 1380 and 1132: ^1H NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_{H} : 0.90 (s, 3H), 1.20-1.96 (m, 7H), 1.98 (s, 3H), 2.08-5.00 (m, 11H), 6.00 (d, 1H, $J = 1.82$ Hz), 7.20 (d, 1H, $J = 1.60$ Hz) ppm. ^{13}C NMR (500 MHz, Chloroform-*d*) δ_{C} : 13.85, 15.87, 21.50, 27.24, 28.42, 30.00, 30.39, 35.74, 39.04, 42.60, 47.38, 50.72, 54.84, 74.90, 122.12, 126.12, 128.34, 130.15, 133.22, 146.91, 175.60, 220.20 ppm. EI-MS m/z : 382.18. Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{26}\text{N}_2\text{O}_4$: C, 69.09; H, 6.85; N, 7.32; O, 16.73. Found: C, 69.00; H, 6.80.

Figure 2. Chemical structure of Nitrobenzyl-dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine-steroid derivatives.

Figure 3. Preparation of oxazepine-steroid derivatives (**5-12**). Reaction of estradiol (**1**) or estrone (**2**) or 4-nitroestradiol (**3**) or 4-nitroestrone (**4**) with (4-Nitro-phenyl)-acetone and 5-hexyn-1-ol (i) to form nitrophenyl-oxepine derivatives (**5-8**). In addition, the 2-Methyl-oxazepine-steroid analogs were prepared from **1-4** and 5-hexyn-1-ol (ii).

Figures (5-8, 10-13)².

Figure 4. Reaction mechanism involved in the synthesis of oxazepine-steroid derivatives.

3. Results and Discussion

There are several reports which showed the preparation of some oxazepine derivatives using different methods and reagents such as 1,4-diazabicyclo[2.2.2]octane [13], rhodium(III) [14], polyphosphoric acid [15] gold chloride [16], phenyliodine(III) [17], Ytterbium(III) trifluoromethanesulfonate [18] and others; however, some of these reagents are expensive, difficult to handle and require special conditions.

3.1. Preparation of nitrophenyl-oxazepine-steroid derivatives

In this study some nitrophenyl-oxazepine-steroid derivative derivatives were prepared using the three-component system (steroid, 4-Nitro-phenyl-acetonitrile and 5-hexyn-1-ol) (90 μ l, 0.82 mmol) and 5 ml of ethanol (Figures 2 and 3).

It is important to mention that in this reaction several factors are involved such as; 1) different type of steroid (**1-4**); 2) the reaction does not require any catalyst or special conditions such happening with other type of reactions [19-21]; 3) the mechanism involves an addition and cyclization reaction to form an oxazepine derivative (Figure 4).

The results (Figure 5) showed several signal of the ¹H NMR spectrum for compound **5** at 0.80 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.12-3.70 and 5.10-5.60 ppm for steroid moiety; at 5.86 and 7.20 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 4.00 ppm for methylene bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.40 ppm for hydroxyl group; at 7.50-8.20 ppm for phenyl group.

² In the field of organic chemistry, chemical displacement of ¹H NMR is measured in units (parts per million, ppm) (X axis). The ¹H NMR signals have an amplitude or intensity independent of the strength of the magnetic field of the equipment where they are recorded (Y axis), but usually, ppm are reported.

Figure 5. The scheme shown ^1H NMR spectrum of **5**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

Figure 6. ^1H NMR spectrum of **6** was determined with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 11.32 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 23.04-31.35, 36.88-113.86, 130.54-130.75 and 149.00 ppm for steroid moiety; at 36.86

ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 121.34, 130.24 and 158.86 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 124.23, 130.53, 141.54 and 149.44 ppm for

phenyl group. Additionally, the mass spectrum from **5** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 460.23.

On the other hand, ^1H NMR spectrum of **6** (Figure 6) showed several signals at 0.90 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.20-3.64 and 5.10-5.60 ppm for steroid moiety; at 4.02 ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 5.86-7.20 for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 7.50-8.20 ppm for phenyl group. The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 13.84 for methyl group; at 21.50-35.74, 39.02, 113.86, 126.59, 133.24 and 150.52 ppm for steroid moiety; at 36.86 ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 121.37, 130.27 and 158.52 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 124.20, 130.53 and 141.52-149.44 ppm for phenyl group; at 220.15 ppm for ketone group. Finally, the mass spectrum from **6** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 458.22.

In addition, ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 7) of **7** showed several signals at 0.80 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.10-3.64 and 4.56-5.10 ppm for steroid moiety; at 4.02 ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.00-7.22 for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.40 ppm for hydroxyl group; at 7.50-8.20 ppm for phenyl group.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 11.32 ppm for methyl group; at 23.02-30.70, 38.31-81.72, 128.40, 130.32, 134.52 and 144.52 ppm for steroid moiety; at 36.86 ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 121.92, 130.16 and 174.84 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 124.20, 130.50-143.82 and 149.44 ppm for phenyl group. In addition, the mass spectrum from **7** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 505.22.

Finally, ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 8) of **8** showed several signals at 0.90 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.20-3.64 and 4.60-5.10 ppm for steroid moiety; at 4.00 ppm for methylene group bound to both phenyl group and dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 121.90, 130.26, and 158.82 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 124.20, 130.50 and 141.53-149.43 ppm for phenyl group; at 220.20 ppm for ketone group. Additionally, the mass spectrum from **8** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 458.22

Figure 7. Visualization of ^1H NMR spectrum from **7**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

3.2. Preparation of 2-Methyl-6,7-dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine-steroid derivatives.

Also, other type of oxazepine-steroid derivatives (Figure 9), were synthesized using the three-component system (steroid, acetonitrile and 5-hexyn-1-ol).

Figure 8. The scheme shown ^1H NMR spectrum from **8**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

The results showed several signal of the ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 10) of **9** showed several signals at 0.80 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.98 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 1.10-1.96 and 2.02-5.60 ppm for steroid moiety; at 5.86-7.20 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.40 ppm for hydroxyl group. The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 11.32 ppm for methyl bound to steroid nucleus; at 15.85 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 23.02-113.80, 126.53 and 130.74-149.90 ppm for steroid moiety; at 121.53, 130.24 and 159.52 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring. Finally, the mass spectrum from **9** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 339.21.

The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 13.87 ppm for methyl bound to steroid nucleus; at 15.86 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 21.53-113.80, 126.59-129.24 and 151.40 ppm for steroid moiety; at 121.52, 130.24 and 159.53 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 220.20 ppm for ketone group. In addition, the mass spectrum from **10** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 337.20.

On the other hand, ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 12) of **11** showed several signals at 0.80 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.98 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 1.10-1.96 and 2.02-5.00 ppm for steroid moiety; at 6.00-7.20 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.40 ppm for hydroxyl group.

Figure 9. Chemical structure of 2-Methyl-6,7-dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine-steroid derivatives.

Figure 10. ^1H NMR spectrum of **9** was determined with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

Figure 11. The scheme shown ^1H NMR spectrum from **10**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

In addition, ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 11) of **10** showed several signals at 0.90 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.98 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine

ring; at 1.20-1.96 and 2.10-5.60 ppm for steroid moiety; at 5.86-7.20 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 6.40 ppm for hydroxyl group.

Figure 12. Visualization of ^1H NMR spectrum from **11**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

Figure 13. The scheme shown ^1H NMR spectrum from **12**. Analyzed with a Varian VXR300/5 FT NMR apparatus at 300 and 75.4 MHz in CDCl_3 .

The ^{13}C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 11.32 ppm for methyl bound to steroid nucleus; at 15.85 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 23.02-81.72, 128.36 and 130.34-145.41 ppm for steroid moiety; at 122.13, 130.12 and 175.41 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine

ring. Finally, the mass spectrum from **11** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 384.20.

Finally, ^1H NMR spectrum (Figure 13) of **12** showed several signals at 0.90 ppm for methyl group bound to steroid nucleus; at 1.98 ppm for

methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 1.20-1.96 and 2.08-5.00 ppm for steroid moiety; at 6.00-7.20 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring. The ¹³C NMR spectra displays chemical shifts at 13.85 ppm for methyl bound to steroid nucleus; at 15.87 ppm for methyl group bound to dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 21.50-74.90, 126.12-128.34 and 133.22-146.91 ppm for steroid moiety; at 122.12, 130.15 and 175.60 ppm for dihydro-[1,3]oxazepine ring; at 220.20 ppm for ketone group. In addition, the mass spectrum from **12** showed a molecular ion (m/z) at 382.18.

4. Conclusions

In this study is reported a method for the preparation of some oxazepine-steroid derivatives using three component system. It is important to mention that reagent used for their preparation was not require special conditions and are facile of handled.

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None

References

- [1] K. Nagarajan, K. D. Kulkarni, Y. Hendi, S. Shenoy, and P. Upadhyaya, "Piperazinylbenzo-naphthoxazepines with CNS Depressant Properties", *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, Vol. 21, **1986**, pp. 21-26.
- [2] G. Walther, H. Daniel, W. Bechtel, K. and Brandt, "New Tetracyclic Guanidine Derivatives with H1-antihistaminic Properties", *Arzneimittel Forschung*, Vol. 40, **1990**, 40, pp. 440-446.
- [3] J. Taunton, J. Collins, and L. Schreiber, "Synthesis of Natural and Modified Trapoxins, Useful Reagents for Exploring Histone Deacetylase Function", *Journal of American Chemical Society*, Vol. 118, 10412-10422.
- [4] E. Karadeniz, and M. Zora, "One-pot Synthesis of 2-Ferrocenyl-substituted Pyridines", *Tetrahedron Letters*, Vol. 57, **2016**, pp. 4930-4934.
- [5] K. Anila, and J. Lincy, G. Mathew, "Synthesis and characterization of novel 5,6 -benz[1,3-oxazepane-4,7-dione derivatives from semicarbazone", *International Journal of Chemical and Pharmaceutical Sciences*, Vol. 7, No. 2, **2016**, pp. 13-20.
- [6] X. Zhao J, Zhang, Z. Zheng, and R. Xu, "Facile Synthesis for Benzo-1,4-Oxazepine Derivatives by Tandem Transformation of C-N Coupling/C-H Carbonylation. *Molecules*", *Molecules*, Vol. 22, No. 1, **2016**, pp. 1-12.
- [7] Y. Wu, C. Yuan, C. Wang, and B. Mao, "Palladium-Catalyzed [5 + 2] Cycloaddition of Vinyloxiranes with Sulfamate-Derived Cyclic Imines To Construct 1,3-Oxazepine Heterocycles", *Organic Letters*, Vol. 19, No. 23, **2017**, pp 6268-6271.
- [8] M. Skvorcova, L. Grigorjeva, and A. Jirgensons, "Tetrahydro-1,3-oxazepines via Intramolecular Amination of Cyclopropylmethyl Cation", *Organic Letters*, Vol. 17, No. 2, **2015**, pp 2902-2904.
- [9] Y. Ok, H. Ji, D. Jung, U. Bin, and S. Lee, "Rh(II)/Mg(O^tBu)₂-Catalyzed Tandem One-Pot Synthesis of 1,4-Oxazepines and 1,4-Oxazines from *N*-Sulfonyl-1,2,3-triazoles and Glycidols", *Organic Letters*, Vol 18, No. 24, **2016**, pp 6432-6435.
- [10] J. Kishore, W. Hu, H. Chen, G. Chandru, C. Chen, and J. Wang, "A New Approach to 1,4-Oxazines and 1,4-Oxazepines via Base-Promoted Exo Mode Cyclization of Alkynyl Alcohols: Mechanism and DFT Studies", *Organic Letters*, Vol. 14, No. 12, **2012**, pp. 3134-3137.
- [11] I. Nakamura, Y. Kudo, M. Terada, "Oxazepine synthesis by copper-catalyzed intermolecular cascade reactions between O-propargylic oximes and dipolarophiles", *Angewandte Chemie International Edition in English*, Vol. 52, No. 29, **2013**, pp. 7536-7539.
- [12] S. Kraychy "Synthesis of Potential Metabolites of Estradiol", *Journal of American Chemistry Society*, Vol. 81, no. 1, **1959**, pp. 1702-1704.
- [13] A. Fugard, B. K. Thompson, A. Slawin, J. Taylor, and A. Smith, "Organocatalytic Synthesis of Fused Bicyclic 2,3-Dihydro-1,3,4-oxadiazoles through an Intramolecular Cascade Cyclization. *Organic Letters*, Vol. 17, No. 23, **2015**, pp. 5824-5827.
- [14] A. Pandey, D. Kang, S. Han, H. Lee, N. Mishra, H. Kim, Y. Jung, S. Hong, and I. Kim, "Reactivity of Morita-Baylis-Hillman Adducts in C-H Functionalization of (Hetero)aryl Nitrones: Access to Bridged Cycles and Carbazoles", *Organic Letters*, Vol. 20, No. 15, **2018**, pp. 4632-4636.

[15] M. Mollo and L. Orelli, “Microwave-Assisted Synthesis of 2-Aryl-2-oxazolines, 5,6-Dihydro-4H-1,3-oxazines, and 4,5,6,7-Tetrahydro-1,3-oxazepines”, *Organic Letters*, Vol. 18, No. 23, **2016**, pp. 6116-6119.

[16] N. Mangina, V. Kadiyala, R. Guduru, K. Goutham, B. Sridhar, and G.Karunakar, “Gold-Catalyzed Intramolecular Regioselective 7-*exo-dig* Cyclization To Access 3-Methylene-3,4-dihydrobenzo[*b*]oxepinones”, *Organic Letters*, Vol. 19, No. 1, **2017**, pp, 282-285.

[17] V. Jamsheena, C. Mahesha, M. Joy, and R. Lankalapalli, “Metal-Free Diaryl Etherification of Tertiary Amines by *Ortho*-C(sp²)-H Functionalization for Synthesis of Dibenzoxazepines and -ones”, *Organic Letters*, Vol. 19, No. 24, **2017**, pp. 6614-6617.

[18] A. Stevens, C. Palmer, and B. Pagenkopf, “The Formal [4+3] Cycloaddition between Donor-Acceptor Cyclobutanes and Nitrones”, *Organic Letters*, Vol. 13, No. 6, **2011**, pp. 1528-1531.

[19] X. Qing, C. Wei, F. Nan, Z. Gang, Z. Shan. “Design and synthesis of 10-alkoxy-5, 6-dihydro-triazolo[4,3-*d*]benzo[*f*][1,4]oxazepine derivatives with anticonvulsant activity”, *European Journal of Medicinal Chemistry*, Vol. 45, No. 7, **2010**, pp. 3080-3086.

[20] R. Yogesh, G. Rajagopal, P. Saikia, R. Pal, “Poly(ethylene glycol) (PEG) as an efficient and recyclable reaction medium for the synthesis of dibenz[*b,f*]-1,4-oxazepine”, *Tetrahedron Letters*. Vol. 49, No. 9, **2008**, pp. 1495-1497.

[21] S. Swapnil, S. Sandip, V. Labade, B. Shingate, M. dhingare, “An Efficient Synthesis and Antibacterial Screening of Novel Oxazepine α -Aminophosphonates by Ultrasound Approach”, *Phosphorus, Sulfur, and Silicon and the Related Elements*, Vol. 185, No. 1, **2010**, pp. 65-73.